

THE INFLUENCE OF WADIAH CONTRACTS (CURRENT ACCOUNT DEPOSITS, SAVINGS DEPOSITS, AND BONUSES) ON NET NON-PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) WITH FIRM SIZE AS A MODERATING VARIABLE IN ISLAMIC BANKING IN INDONESIA PERIOD 2018.Q1 – 2023.Q3

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ABSTRACT

This research analyzes the influence of Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Wadiah Bonuses on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF), with Firm Size as a moderating variable in Islamic banking in Indonesia. Panel data from 5 sharia banks (Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Bukopin Syariah, BCA Syariah, and Bank Aceh Syariah) for the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3 was processed using panel data regression and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). The research results show: 1) Wadiah Giro Savings, Wadiah Savings, and Wadiah Bonuses have an effect on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) nett; 2) Firm size is able to moderate the influence of Wadiah Current Account Deposits and Wadiah Savings Deposits. Meanwhile, Firm size is unable to moderate the influence of Wadiah Bonuses on Non-Performing Financing Nett in Sharia Banking in 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. In future research, it is hoped that variables other than those that can be moderating variables can be used. Furthermore, we suggest that further research should not only look at the company from a financial perspective, but also from other parts of the company so that the findings can be reflected in other areas of the company.

Keywords: *Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, Savings Investment Funds, Deposit Investment Funds, Wadiah Bonuses, Non-Performing Financing (NPF) Net, Firm Size, Islamic Bank*

I. INTRODUCTION

Sharia banks are banks that carry out their business activities based on the principles of Islamic law in banking activities based on fatwas issued by the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulama Council (Ansori, 2018). Sharia banking in Indonesia has experienced quite rapid growth over the last few decades. This can be seen from the growth in assets, third party financing and quite large financing. Based on data

from the Financial Services Authority (OJK), sharia bank assets in December 2022 reached IDR 238.3 trillion, an increase of 12.22% compared to the previous year of IDR 4.444 trillion (Financial Services Authority, 2023).

This growth was also accompanied by an increase in the number of sharia banks, which initially were only 5 banks in 1992 and increased to 30 banks in 2023 (Shandy Utama, 2018). One of the main sharia banking products is wadiah deposits, namely deposits of customer funds that do not receive compensation. Islamic banks also offer wadiah savings, which are wadiah savings that are complemented by other banking services such as ATM cards and internet banking. As a form of appreciation to customers, Islamic banks can provide wadiah bonuses, namely non-obligatory rewards for wadiah funds deposited (Neli, 2020).

One indicator of the growth of Islamic banks is third party funds, assets owned and financing. Third party funds refer to sources of funds from the public, where financial institutions collect funds from the public or customers. Wadiah demand deposits and wadiah savings are sharia banking products used for accumulation and (Andriani & Pakkanna, 2020). The contract applied in this case is the wadiah contract, which allows customers to entrust their funds to the bank. There are two types of wadiah contracts, namely Wadiah Yad Amanah and Wadiah Yad Dhamanah. In the Wadiah Yad Amanah contract, the customer purely entrusts funds to the bank, which is then responsible for the deposit. Meanwhile, the Wadiah Yad Dhamanah agreement allows the customer as the depositor/owner to give the Sharia Bank the right to manage the deposited funds for productive activities.

Wadiah deposits, wadiah savings and wadiah bonuses are the main sources of funds for sharia financial institutions, especially sharia banks. These funds are used to fund various bank business activities, including financing to customers. Financing quality, as measured by NPF, is an important indicator of a bank's financial health. A high NPF indicates that many bank customers are unable to repay their loans, which can threaten the bank's financial stability. Previous research has shown a relationship between wadiah deposits, wadiah savings and wadiah bonuses with the quality of financing (NPF) in sharia banks (Sari, 2021). However, the results of these studies vary and do not take into account the role of firm size as a moderating variable. The size of the bank can influence the bank's ability to manage financing risks, so that it can influence the relationship between wadiah deposits, wadiah savings, wadiah bonuses and NPF.

The aim of this research is to analyze the influence of Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Wadiah Bonuses on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF), with Firm Size as a moderating variable in Islamic banking in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Wadiah Current Account Savings

Current accounts are deposits from which withdrawals can be made at any time using a check, giro bill, other means of payment order or by transfer. In the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council, provisions regarding Wadiah Giro are stipulated, namely

that it is a deposit, the deposit can be taken at any time, and no compensation is required, except in the form of voluntary gifts (Ministry of Religion, 2003).

2.2 Wadiah Savings Deposits

Savings Deposits is one of the sharia bank fund collection products in the form of a savings account for security and ease of use. The means for withdrawing Wadiah Savings itself can be in the form of withdrawal slips, ATMs, savings books, etc. (Sunreni, 2019). In other sources, wadiah savings are a type of savings that function as a pure deposit, which must be maintained and returned according to the wishes of the fund owner (customer). Profits or losses resulting from the distribution of funds or use of goods are the sole property or responsibility of the bank. The customer, as the depositor, is not promised any compensation and does not bear any losses (Rohmah & Fauzi, 2021).

2.3 Prize bonus

Bonuses are given to bank accounts that have a wadiah balance as a reward or incentive. The money is sent to the wadiah account as a form of payment after the bank deposits the money. Because the bonus is not paid in full, p. This ultimately becomes bank policy (Novianto, 2021).

2.4 Non-Performing Financing (NPF) Nett

Non-Performing Financing (NPF) nett is a bad indicator which is important to examine with special attention, an indicator to be examined carefully because it needs to be directed at its stable and not constant nature. Its unstable nature makes it important to be examined with careful consideration. It is important to examine it with careful consideration (Popita, 2013).

2.5 Firm Size

Business size The term "size " refers to the size of a business which is determined by the total number of active members, number of transactions, transaction volume, and average number of transactions. The term "size " refers to the size of a business which is determined by its overall activities, transaction volume, number of transactions, and average transaction size. When compared to small businesses, large businesses will find it easier to manage their reputation because they are more established. to improve their reputation (Tiong et al., 2022). Businesses with relatively large turnover rates have relatively high turnover rates compared to small businesses, which means that when looking at their return on equity (ROE) they are higher than small businesses. The turnover rate of businesses has a higher turnover rate compared to small businesses, which means that when viewed from the return on equity (ROE) they are higher compared to small businesses. (ROE) compared to small businesses, which is an indication of their business. compared to small businesses, which is an indication of their business. As a result, there will be less trust in large companies that expect high returns. Results, investors will be less trusting in large companies that expect high profits (Oi & Idson, 1999).

2.6 Effect of Wadiah Current Account Savings on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) Nett (H1)

In previous research, it was explained that Wadiah giro savings have a positive impact on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in sharia banking through several main ways. The stability and liquidity of wadiah demand deposits, which are interest-free and have low volatility, help Islamic banks maintain good liquidity, so that the risk of financing problems is reduced. This fund stability also provides banks with more flexibility in managing their financing portfolio, enabling more careful financing selection to reduce NPF. In addition, because wadiah giro does not pay interest, the cost of funds is lower, allowing banks to offer financing with competitive margins that attract quality customers with low risk of default. With better liquidity, bank operational efficiency increases, strengthening the bank's ability to monitor and manage financing risks, thereby reducing NPF (Abdul-rahman & Nor, 2016).

2.7 Effect of Wadiah Savings Deposits on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) Nett (H2)

In previous research, it was explained that wadiah savings deposits have a positive impact on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in sharia banking through several main mechanisms. This type of savings provides good liquidity and stability of funds because it does not carry interest and has a more stable balance, thereby helping banks meet short-term obligations without having to sell risky assets. The stability of these funds allows banks to manage financing risks more efficiently, plan more appropriate financing strategies, and reduce uncertainty. In addition, the low cost of funds due to no rewards to customers allows banks to offer financing products with competitive margins, attracting customers with a low risk profile who are better able to meet their obligations. With better liquidity, banks can diversify their financing portfolio, reduce risk concentration in certain sectors, and reduce the possibility of NPF occurrence (Abdul-rahman & Nor, 2016). Wadiah savings contribute to Islamic banks by maintaining good liquidity, managing financing risks more efficiently, reducing the cost of funds, and diversifying the financing portfolio. Overall, this helps reduce the level of Non-Performing Financing (NPF) (Fatimah & Hamdan Ainullyaqin, 2022).

2.8 Effect of Wadiah Bonus on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) nett (H3)

In previous research, it was explained that the Wadiah Bonus had a positive impact on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in Islamic banking through several mechanisms. Firstly, these bonuses increase customer loyalty, so they are more likely to continue saving and using the bank's services, which helps maintain liquidity. Second, the Wadiah bonus provides an incentive for customers to keep their funds in the bank, increasing liquidity which allows the bank to channel financing more flexibly, reducing the risk of default. Third, increasing managed funds allows Islamic banks to increase operational efficiency, which supports the ability to better manage financing and reduce the risk of default. Finally, additional funds from Wadiah

bonuses give banks the ability to be more selective in channeling financing, choosing projects or customers with low risk, which helps reduce NPF (Barus, 2019).

2.9 The Effect of Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Wadiah Bonuses on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) (H4)

In previous research, it was explained that Wadiah Current Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Wadiah Bonuses all contributed positively to the decrease in Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in Islamic banks. Wadiah demand deposits increase liquidity and provide stable, untied funds, enabling more effective risk management and flexibility in managing financing, thereby reducing the risk of default. Likewise, wadiah savings deposits increase liquidity, allow banks to meet short-term financial obligations and support more selective financing, which lowers potential NPFs. Wadiah bonuses increase customer loyalty and the amount of funds managed by the bank, increase operational efficiency and provide greater flexibility in channeling financing wisely, thereby reducing the risk of default and helping to reduce NPF (Maratul Munawaroh et al., 2022).

2.10 The Effect of Wadiah Current Account Savings on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) at Firm Size Moderation (H5)

Research on the influence of wadiah demand deposits on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) has developed from an initial focus on the 2000-2010 period, which showed a positive and significant influence of wadiah demand deposits on NPF without considering the moderating variable, namely firm size. In 2010-2020, research began to evaluate the moderating variable, namely firm size, finding that large financial institutions were better able to mitigate NPF risk than small banks. In the 2020-present period, the research expanded its focus to other factors such as bank assets, bank efficiency, and capital adequacy ratios, with company size remaining an important moderating variable, strengthening the finding that large banks are more effective in managing NPF risk (Setiawan & Suwaidi, 2022).

2.11 The Effect of Wadiah Savings Deposits on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) at Firm Size Moderation (H6)

The evolution of the mortgage insurance industry towards non-performing financing (NPF) has been observed over the past few years. In the 2000-2010 period, research focused on the long-term impact of NPF, showing a positive and significant impact without considering company size. However, during the 2010-2020 period, research began to analyze company size as a moderating variable, with the finding that large banks were better able to mitigate NPF risk than small banks, as well as showing a positive correlation between bank size and NPF. Currently, research is increasingly examining several other factors that can have an impact on the relationship between Non-Performing Financing (NPF) and Wadiah, such as bank quality, operational efficiency, capital adequacy ratio, and financial literacy threshold. Company size (Firm Size) remains an important moderating variable in this context. It is anticipated that future research will continue to explore other factors that influence this

relationship and how these factors may differ when looking at different bank sizes. Overall, the research shows that company size is a significant moderating variable in the relationship between NPF and Wadiah.

2.12 The Effect of Wadiah Bonus on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in Firm Size Moderation (H7)

Research on the influence of Wadiah bonuses on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) has developed from the 2000-2010 to 2020-present period. Initially, research showed a positive and significant impact of Wadiah bonuses on NPF without considering company size. During the 2010-2020 period, company size began to be considered as a moderating variable, and the results show that company size strengthens the positive effect of Wadiah bonuses on NPF, with large banks being better able to manage NPF than small banks. Since 2020, research has focused on additional factors such as bank assets, bank efficiency, capital adequacy ratio, financial literacy, and the Wadiah bonus mechanism, with company size remaining an important moderating variable. Future research is expected to continue to examine other factors that influence this relationship at different scales.

2.13 Effect of Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, Wadiah Bonus simultaneously on Non Performing Financing (NPF) nett (H7)

The effect of Non-Performing Financing (NPF) is simultaneously felt by Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, Savings Investment Funds, Deposit Investment Funds, and Wadiah Bonuses. An important consideration in the financial industry is the collective impact of various types of investments and savings, including wadiah incentives, on NPF. This study examines how each type of investment and savings, along with wadiah incentives, collectively affects net present value. a real estate company. The results of this simultaneous analysis allow a more comprehensive understanding of how the combination of factors such as Wadiah Current Accounts, Wadiah Savings Deposits, Savings Investment Funds, Deposit Investment Funds, and Wadiah Bonuses affect the credit portfolio of banks or other financial institutions.

The following is the correlation of the independent and dependent variables

III. METHODOLOGY

The method used for this investigation is a quantitative method. The data used for this research is second level data obtained from ojk.go.id or related company websites. The most popular currency in 2015 is banknotes. Quarter 1 of 2023.Q3 uses a purposive sampling technique. The sample used consisted of several financial reports from banking companies for 2015. Quarter 1 of 2023. Q3, resulting in a total sample of 105 financial reports from 2015 to 2023.

The data analysis methods used in this research include Panel Regression Modeling and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Acceptable correlation, also known as Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), uses analytical techniques that maintain sample integrity and provide a basis for determining moderator effects (Ghozali, 2018). The following is a comparison of panel data regression analysis models:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Non-Performing Financing (NPF) nett

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Wadiah Giro Savings

X2 = Wadiah Savings Deposits

X3 = Wadiah Bonus

e_i = Error

In this study, the hypothesis is investigated through regression analysis involving moderating variables. In Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), the regression equation considers the correlation between variables using the following equation formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4Z + \beta_5X_1*Z + \beta_6X_2*Z + \beta_7X_3*Z + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Non-Performing Financing (NPF) nett

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Wadiah Giro Savings

X2 = Wadiah Savings Deposits

X3 = Wadiah Bonus

Z = Firm Size

X1*Z = Correlation of the influence of Wadiah Current Account Savings with firm size moderation

X2*Z = Correlation of the influence of Wadiah Savings Savings with firm size moderation

X3*Z = Correlation of the influence of the Wadiah Bonus with firm size moderation

e_i = Error.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

	X1	X2	X3	Y	Z
Mean	3648583.	5412123	19760.50	1.870087	17.00652
Maximum	27797852	4421	277538.0	4.980000	19.58000
Minimum	158228.0	714	261.0000	0.000000	15.45000
Std. Dev.	6544026.	1088	40830.74	1.951439	1.150835
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

According to the data in Table 1, it can be ascertained that the total number of studies in the banking sector in 2018 was 115 studies. Q1 2023. Q3. According to the descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be ascertained that the Wadiah Current Account Savings variable has a mean of 3648583, a maximum of 27797852, a minimum of 158228.0, and a standard deviation of 6544026.

According to the descriptive statistics in Table 1, the Wadiah Savings Accounts variable (X2) has a mean of 5412123, a maximum of 44214405, a minimum of 71477.00, and a standard deviation of 10888656.

According to the descriptive statistics in Table 1, the Wadiah Bonus variable (X3) has a mean of 19760.50, a maximum of 277538.0, a minimum of 261.0000, and a standard deviation of 40830.74.

According to the descriptive statistics in Table 1, the NPF (Y) variable has a mean of 1.870087, a maximum of 4.980000, a minimum of 0.000000, and a standard deviation of 1.951439.

4.2 PANEL DATA REGRESSION MODEL SELECTION

Selection of a panel data regression model is an analysis stage that functions to determine the best method between Common Effect, Fixed Effect, or Random Effect

CHOW TEST

This test is used to determine the best model between the Common Effect Model (and the Fixed Effect Model.

Table 2. CHOW TEST Results

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	11.473451	(4,106)	0.0000
Chi-square cross-section	41.370390	4	0.0000

According to the results of Table 2, the chi-square cross-section probability value is $0.0000 < 0.05$. Thus, it can be ascertained that the better model to determine is the Fixed Effect Model.

HAUSMAN TEST

This test functions to determine which is better between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 3
HAUSMAN TEST Results

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Random cross-section	79.052104	4	0.0000

According to the figure in table 3, it can be proven that the test results above reveal a probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$. So it can be confirmed that in this test, the better model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

4.3 CLASSIC ASSUMPTION TEST
TEST FOR NORMALITY

Table 4. NORMALITY TEST

According to table 4 above, it shows that the Jarque-Bera probability value is 3.864189.. So it can be confirmed that the data in this study is normally distributed.

MULTICOLINERITY TEST

Table 5. MULTICOLLINERITY TEST

	LOG_X2	X1	X3
LOG_X2	1,000000	0.751205	0.391260
X1	0.751205	1,000000	0.310680
X3	0.391260	0.310680	1,000000

According to the test results in table 5 above, it can be stated that the correlation value between the independent variables of all independent variables is below 0.5. Therefore, if the research data cannot be multicollinearity between independent variables except for the correlation of X1 with X3

HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST

Table 6. HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	0.185775	0.026967	6.888871	0.0000
X1	3.04E-09	9.85E-09	0.308102	0.7586
X2	-1.02E-08	7.01E-09	-1.460057	0.1472
X3	-1.09E-06	7.16E-07	-1.518469	0.1318

According to the table above, the test above can be stated that the probability value of the result is more than 0.5. A regression model is said to not be subject to heteroscedasticity if it has a probability value of more than 0.5. Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression model used in this research does not experience heteroscedasticity. Except for variables x1 and x3

4.4 PANEL DATA REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Panel data regression analysis uses a more efficient model, namely the Fixed Effect Model regression as shown in the following table:

Table 7. REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF FIXED EFFECT MODEL PANEL DATA

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	-3.30E-07	1.07E-07	-3.090068	0.0025
X2	1.58E-07	6.19E-08	2.558962	0.0118
X3	1.14E-05	5.06E-06	2.247569	0.0266
C	1.991076	0.208610	9.544486	0.0000

MODERATE REGRESSION ANALYSIS (MRA)

Variables that are able to strengthen and vice versa weaken the correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable are usually called moderating variables. The following are the test results in this analysis as follows:

Table 8. MODERATION REGRESSION ANALYSIS TEST

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	-1.81E-06	1.32E-06	-1.366320	0.1748
X2	-3.14E-06	1.52E-06	-2.067314	0.0412
Z	-1.408526	0.658925	-2.137614	0.0349
X3Z	1.09E-07	4.88E-06	0.022384	0.9822

X2Z	1.55E-07	7.66E-08	2.023286	0.0456
X3	-2.21E-06	8.88E-05	-0.024947	0.9801
X1Z	9.65E-08	7.10E-08	1.360324	0.1767
C	27.08591	10.89706	2.485616	0.0145

4.5 STATISTICAL TESTS

T TEST

The T test is used to test whether the relationship between each dependent variable has a prominent influence on the independent variable. Likewise, it is used to be able to analyze the reciprocity of each independent variable on the dependent variable tested with a benchmark of 0.5 or with a confidence level of 95% and an error rate of 5%.

According to the t test (partial) that the author has carried out in this research, it can be proven that the results processed from the t test are as follows:

1. Hypothesis 1 (H1): Wadiah Current Account Savings have an influence on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF).
2. With a probability value of 0.1748, which means it is smaller than the prominent value of 0.5 or 5%. This reveals that Wadiah Current Account Savings have an influence on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in banking sector companies for the period 2018.Q1–2023.Q3.
3. Hypothesis 2 (H2): Wadiah Savings Deposits have an influence on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF). With a probability value of 0.0412 1748, which means it is smaller than the prominent value of 0.5 or 5%. This reveals that Wadiah Savings Deposits have an influence on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in banking sector companies for the period 2018.Q1–2023.Q3.
4. Hypothesis 3 (H3): Wadiah Bonus has no influence on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF). With a probability value of 0.9801, which means it is greater than the salient value of 0.5 or 5%. This reveals that the Wadiah Bonus has no effect on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in banking sector companies for the period 2018.Q1–2023.Q3.
5. Hypothesis 4 (H4): Wadiah Current Account Savings has an effect on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) which is moderated by firm size. With a probability value of 0.1767 1748, which means it is smaller than the prominent value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that firm size can moderate Wadiah Current Account Savings in Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in banking sector companies for the period 2018.Q1–2023.Q3.
6. Hypothesis 5 (H5): Wadiah Savings Deposits have an effect on nett Non-Performing Financing (NPF) moderated by firm size with a probability value of 0.0456, which means it is smaller than the prominent value of 0.5 or 5 %. This shows that firm size can moderate Wadiah Savings Deposits in Non-Performing Financing (NPF) in banking sector companies for the period 2018.Q1–2023.Q3.

7. Hypothesis 6 (H6) : Wadiah bonuses have an effect on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) which is moderated by firm size. With a probability value of 0.9822, which means it is greater than the prominent value of 0.5 or 5. This shows that firm size cannot moderate the Wadiah Bonus on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) nett in banking sector companies for the quarter of 2018.Q1–2023.Q3.

TEST F

The F test is used to test whether the independent variable has a prominent effect on the dependent variable simultaneously. Following are the results of the F test.

Table 10. F TEST RESULTS

Prob(F-statistic) 0.000000

Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

The F test in this study uses a salient value of 0.5 or 5% with the rule that if the salient value of $F < 0.5$ then the regression coefficient is appropriate to use. The F test results in table 10 above reveal a prominent F value of 0.000000, this value is smaller than the salient value, namely 0.5. So, it can be ascertained that institutional ownership and capital structure simultaneously have an influence on company value.

DETERMINATION COEFFICIENT TEST

The Determination Coefficient is used with the aim of revealing the role of the independent variable in the regression model in revealing the dependent variable.

Table 11. DETERMINATION COEFFICIENT TEST RESULTS

Adjusted R-squared 0.810071

According to table 11, the results of the panel data regression test on Murabahah Receivables as the dependent variable, reveal that the Adjusted R² value is 0.810071. This can be interpreted to mean that 81.00 % of the company value variable can be expressed by institutional ownership and capital structure. Meanwhile, the rest can be expressed by other variables outside the regression model

4.6 DISCUSSION

The Effect of Wadiah Current Account Savings on Npf Nett

According to table 9, the results of this test reveal that the probability value for Wadiah Giro Savings is 0.1748, which means less than 0.5. The test results also reveal a negative direction with a coefficient value of -1.81E-06 and t-statistic -1.366320. So it reveals that Wadiah Current Account Savings has a good effect on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF). So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H1: Wadiah Current Account Savings has an effect on nett Non-Performing Financing (NPF), is accepted.

This is in accordance with previous research regarding the positive impact of Wadiah demand deposits on Non-Performing Financing (NPF). In this study, Wadiah giro does not provide interest, the cost of funds is lower, allowing banks to offer financing with competitive margins that attract quality customers with low risk of default. With better liquidity, bank operational efficiency increases, strengthening the bank's ability to monitor and manage financing risks, thereby reducing NPF (Sari, 2021) .

The Effect of Wadiah Savings on Net NPF

According to table 9, the results of this test reveal that the probability value for Wadiah Savings Savings is 0.0412, which means less than 0.5. The test results also reveal a negative direction with a coefficient value of $-2.21E-06$ and t-statistic -2.067314 . So it reveals that Wadiah Savings Deposits have a negative effect on Non-Performing Financing Nett. So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher, namely H2: Wadiah Savings Savings has an effect on Non-Performing Financing Nett, is accepted. This hypothesis is strengthened by previous research regarding Wadiah Savings Wadiah savings contribute to Islamic banks by maintaining good liquidity, managing financing risks more efficiently, reducing the cost of funds, and diversifying the financing portfolio. Overall, this helps reduce the level of Non-Performing Financing (NPF).

The Effect of Wadiah Bonus on NPF Nett

According to table 9, the results of this test reveal that the probability value for the Wadiah Bonus is 0.9801, which means more than 0.5. The test results also reveal a negative direction with a coefficient value of -2.885415 and t-statistic -0.024947 . Therefore, it is revealed that the Wadiah Bonus has a negative effect on Non-Performing Financing Nett. So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher is H3: Wadiah Bonus has an effect on nett Non-Performing Financing (NPF) and is accepted.

Firm size moderates the influence of Wadiah Current Accounts, Wadiah Savings and Wadiah Bonuses on Net Non-Performing Financing (NPF)

According to table 9, the results of this test reveal that the correlation probability value between Wadiah Current Account Savings and firm size is 0.1767, which means it is smaller than 0.5. The test results also reveal a positive direction with a coefficient value of $9.65E-08$ and a t-statistic of 1.360324. These results reveal that profitability can strengthen the influence between Wadiah Current Account Savings and Non-Performing Financing Nett. So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher is H4: Firm size moderates the influence of Wadiah Current Account Savings on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) net acceptance.

This is in accordance with previous research which stated the positive impact of Wadiah Current Accounts, Wadiah Savings Deposits and Wadiah Bonuses on net Non-Performing Financing (NPF). The results of this research state that Wadiah demand deposits increase liquidity and provide stable, untied funds, enabling more effective risk management and flexibility in managing financing, thereby reducing the risk of default. Likewise, wadiah savings deposits increase liquidity, allow banks

to meet short-term financial obligations and support more selective financing, which lowers potential NPFs. Wadiah bonuses increase customer loyalty and the amount of funds managed by the bank, increase operational efficiency and provide greater flexibility in channeling financing wisely, thereby reducing the risk of default and helping to reduce NPF (Popita, 2013) .

Wadiah Savings Deposits Against Net NPF with Firm size as Moderation

According to table 9, the results of this test reveal that the correlation probability value between Wadiah firm size savings accounts is 0.0456, which means it is smaller than 0.5. The test results also reveal a good direction with a coefficient value of 1.55E-07 and a t-statistic of 2.023286. These results reveal that profitability can strengthen the influence between Wadiah Savings Savings and Non-Performing Financing Nett. So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher is H5: Firm size moderates the influence of Wadiah Savings Deposits on Non-Performing Financing (NPF) net acceptance.

Wadiah Bonus to Net NPF with Firm size as Moderation

According to table 9, the results of this test reveal that the correlation probability value between the Wadiah Bonus and firm size is 0.9822, which means it is greater than 0.5. The test results also reveal a good direction with a coefficient value of 1.09E-07 and a t-statistic of 0.022384. These results reveal that profitability can strengthen the influence between Wadiah Bonus and Non-Performing Financing Nett. So the hypothesis proposed by researchers, namely H6: Firm size moderates the influence of Wadiah Bonuses on nett Non-Performing Financing (NPF), is not accepted.

Wadiah Giro Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Wadiah Bonuses Simultaneously Influence Net NPF

According to the calculations in table 10, it can be ascertained that the variables Wadiah Savings Savings, Wadiag Savings Savings and Wadiah Bonus have a prominent influence on nett Non-Performing Financing (NPF). This is because the prominent value is $0.000000 < 0.05$. These results reveal that the influence of Wadiah savings deposits, Wadiag savings deposits and Wadiah bonuses have a simultaneous effect on nett Non-Performing Financing (NPF). So the hypothesis proposed by the researcher is H7: Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Wadiah Bonuses Simultaneously influence Non-Performing Financing Nett.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of tests carried out in this research, it was found that wadiah demand deposits and wadiah savings deposits had a significant influence on the net Non-Performing Financing (NPF) level in the banking sector during the 2018Q1 to 2023Q3 period. This finding is supported by the probability value which is below 0.05 which is the reference value, as well as the coefficient value which shows a negative direction between wadiah current account savings and net NPF. Therefore, these two variables tend to increase the net NPF level in banking companies. On the other hand, giving wadiah bonuses also does not have a significant effect, even though the

direction is positive, which shows that an increase in the amount of wadiah bonuses tends to cause a decrease in the net NPF level.

The research "Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and Current Year Wadiah Bonuses on Non-Performing Financing Nett with Firm Size as Moderation Variables in Sharia Banking in Indonesia for the Period 2018.Q1 - 2023" revealed that Wadiah Current Account Deposits, Wadiah Savings Deposits, and the Wadiah Bonus has a good effect on the Non-Performing Financing Nett of a bank, with a company's measurement as a moderating variable

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